

STRENGTHENING RESEARCH, INNOVATION, AND INDUSTRY COOPERATION IN AUTONOMOUS AERIAL SYSTEMS THROUGH AN INTEGRATED COLLABORATIVE FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

In this work the main experiences and results from the Horizon Europe AeroSTREAM project are shown, as an example of good practice and a framework for replication in other sectors. Building on H2020 AeroTwin project, which focused on reducing the existing gap between universities in the so-called 'widening countries' and European technology leaders in the field of aerial robotics, AeroSTREAM project is conceived as an effort to stream AeroTwin positive effects on a network of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina in order to widen the capacity for research and innovation, and to prepare and establish a long lasting and integrated cooperation between those institutions and their partners in the local ecosystem. The long lasting and integrated cooperation between institutions has been established in the field of unmanned aerial systems (UAS) applications, with emphasis on smart agriculture, forestry, and logistics. To achieve the project objectives, an innovative and integrating cooperation framework has been designed for the different actors involved, including researchers, technology centres, industries, SMEs, public institutions, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), among others. The designed integrated cooperation framework includes the following activities: i) staff exchanges in the form of short-term visits, ii) expert visits, iii) workshops and tutorials at leading conferences, iv) hands-on training, v) innovation management and technology transfer training, and vi) mentoring by leading scientists, which will encourage talented students to stay in the widening countries, which in turn will improve the countries' networking and reputation in general. As a result, the scientific and innovation capacities of all actors in the R&I system in the widening countries have increased, leading to a modernised and more competitive R&I system, stronger links between academia and business, better career permeability and improved international outreach for all actors. The main novelty of this work is the multidisciplinary collaboration between the widening countries and the European technology leaders in the field of aerial robotics, one of the most promising and widely applied sectors today. In addition to the application of knowledge to several sectors and the creation of a unique framework for cooperation at European level between different types of entities and actors from different sectors.

Keywords: Widening countries, Industry cooperation, Aerial robotics, Research Excellence.

1 INTRODUCTION

The main area of application of AeroSTREAM project are Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), also known as drones, which have taken the world by storm. Over the past ten years, miniaturisation, and cost reduction of their components, largely driven by the portable electronics industry, have democratised research and led to the commercialisation of small UAVs for a general public at smartphone prices. Small UAVs for professional use are also increasingly adopted in important socioeconomic sectors, such as environmental monitoring, agriculture, security, infrastructure inspection, and disaster mitigation [1].

This demand has resulted in a booming UAV-related industry. According to recent reports by Drone Industry Insight, the value of the UAV market worldwide is 26.3 billion USD and will rise to 39.3 billion USD by 2025, which makes it one of the fastest growing markets. Despite the pandemic, the investment in the UAV industry reached a new record in 2020 with 2.3 billion USD, which is almost

twice the amount from the previous year (1.3 billion USD) [2]. The European region has played a pioneering role in advancing the science, technology, and application of UAVs by leveraging a long-standing academic tradition in robotics, embedded control, autonomous systems, and bioinspired systems. Several European countries host excellent academic research labs and companies in aerial systems [4].

AeroSTREAM project is focused on Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina (widening countries) to widen their capacity for research and innovation, and to prepare and establish a long lasting and integrated cooperation between these institutions and their partners in the local ecosystem.

Within this framework, the AeroSTREAM project strives to enhance the R&D capacity of the following widening Higher Education Institutions (w-HEIs): the University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (UNIZG-FER), the University of Zagreb Faculty of Traffic and Transportation Sciences (UNIZG-FTTS), the University of Zagreb Faculty of Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture and the University of Sarajevo Faculty of Electrical Engineering.

To reach the main goal of the project, the following sub-objectives have been defined: i) Integrated and long term cooperation between HEIs from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, with partners from Spain, Czech Republic, and the Netherlands in the field of autonomous aerial systems applications, with emphasis on smart agriculture, forestry, and logistics; ii) Increase scientific excellence profiles of HEIs from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina in the field of autonomous aerial systems, and share capacities with partners from Spain, Czech Republic, and the Netherlands; iii) Improve quality of innovation management, technology transfer and citizen involvement of HEIs from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. These objectives will be achieved through a long-lasting and integrated cooperation between institutions will be established in the field of Autonomous Aerial Systems (AAS) applications, with emphasis on smart agriculture, forestry, and logistics.

1.1. Smart Agriculture

Human impact on our ecosystem is widespread, for the most part irreversible and intensifying. Even though heavy industry, traffic, and plastic pollution are the first to blame, agriculture remains a significant contributor to world pollution ([3],[5]). AAS fits perfectly as technology that can be used to improve the environmental performance of farms [6]. In this area, particular emphasis will be given to i) crop health monitoring and creating maps prescription and, ii) weed and pest management - spraying.

1.2. Forestry

Forestry is one of the focal points of the European Green Deal, directly related to attempts to stop environmental degradation of biodiversity. The use of UAV in precision forestry has exponentially increased in the last few years as demonstrated by many papers published during that period ([7], [8]). AAS are in high interest for forest inventorying because of their capability to collect data from which a suite of essential forest inventory attributes can be derived with accuracy close to field inventories. Emphasis will be given to i) inventory resources, map diseases and species classification and ii) fire monitoring and spatial gaps estimation.

1.3. Logistics

AAS can perform several tasks across the logistics sector, including warehouse operations and last-mile delivery [9]. The latter relates to delivery of individual orders to the customer doorsteps in suburban and urban areas using UAVs, which are unimpeded by road congestion. The last mile of delivery is currently the least efficient part of the logistics supply chain, amounting for 50% of the total cost to deliver. The use of AAS will significantly reduce the cost and would have a lower environmental impact. Intra-logistics purposes, such as inventory management and transport of items, come with a different set of challenges and benefits. Emphasis will be given to i) delivery planning and UAV path optimization and ii) perception and autonomy

The contribution of the work is to show the methodology developed within the AeroSTREAM project for sharing knowledge and experience between experienced European partners to Higher Education Institutions from widening countries (w-HEIs) and to show the first results achieved within the first year of the project.

The paper is organised as follows: Section 2 shows the methodology developed within the AeroSTREAM project to achieve the project objectives, Section 3 describes some initial actions and

results within the first year of the project, and Section 4 sums up the achieved goals and describes the actions for the future.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this section we describe in detail actions that are planned during the project. Each action is put in relation to the corresponding objective that it contributes to.

2.1 Towards Objective 1

First objective is integrated and long-term cooperation between HEIs from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, with partners from Spain, Czech Republic, and the Netherlands in the field of autonomous aerial systems applications, with emphasis on smart agriculture, forestry, and logistics.

This Objective will be achieved through the following actions i) Developing shared research strategy; ii) Preparation of action plan for long term cooperation; iii) Preparation to embark on the future European Universities Initiative.

The goal is to conduct an in-depth SWOT overview of w-HEIs through surveys, interviews, and round tables, that will serve as a ground for joint research and innovation strategy, as well as plan for a long-term cooperation. This action will instead build a set of activities that will result in an action plan for long term cooperation for the period 2022 - 2030, that will encompass not only cooperation on research topics, but also the network's common education strategy and regional engagement. For that purpose, among other actions, we will organise 4 round tables with the policy makers, and NCPs, in the first two years of the project. Through meetings with European Universities Initiatives, we will start to prepare the consortium members for the future active participation in such European Universities.

2.2 Towards Objective 2

Increase scientific excellence profiles of w-HEIs in the field of autonomous aerial systems, and share capacities with partners from Spain, Czech Republic, and the Netherlands. This objective will be achieved through:

2.2.1. Short-term visits

The leading HEIs project partners will host research staff members from w-HEIs, where the main purpose of short-term visits is to provide w-HEIs research staff with the opportunity to work together with top scientists from networking institutions daily in laboratories that are equipped with the state-of-the-art equipment.

2.2.2. Co-supervising PhD students

This action will additionally raise the research profile of w-HEIs research staff in two ways: i) PhD students will have the opportunity to be directly supervised by top scientists from the aerial robotics field, ii) partners will join w-HEIs professors in supervision of PhD students which will bring new insights of best practices in education of future scientists.

2.2.3. Expert visits

This activity includes visits of experts from internationally leading partner institutions to w-HEIs. The purpose of expert visits is the transfer of theoretical knowledge, closely related to defined ARs, through a series of lectures.

2.2.4. Summer schools and hands-on trainings

Within this action joint summer schools and hands-on training will be organised with the main purpose of those events is to provide extensive transfer of practical knowledge in a few days, followed by several days dedicated to the implementation of learned techniques on real systems.

2.3 Towards Objective 3

Improve quality of innovation management, technology transfer and citizen involvement of HEIs from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina. Activities dedicated to reinforcing cooperation in research and innovation with other sectors address lack of innovation capacity and strategy, as well as insufficiency

in the entrepreneurial mind-set of researchers and deficiency in cooperation with industry sectors. Further activities are related to embedding citizens and society.

2.3.1. Strengthening innovation capacity

Short-term visits are planned for w-HEI project innovation management staff. The goal of the short-term visits for project management staff is to provide w-HEIs project management staff with direct insight into administrative processes that are related to innovation management and technology transfer.

2.3.2. Mainstreaming entrepreneurial mind-set of researchers

Within this topic innovation management trainings and technology transfer workshops will be organised, promoting the collaboration between them, and defining previously the topics according to their needs.

2.3.3. End-user oriented workshops

End-users workshops will be organised in a form of half-day event with the main goal to give end-users insights into technologies developed by the consortium partners. Three workshops will be organised by Protostar Labs and ICENT, and four by LARICS and CTA. Two of them will be organised as a part of DroneDays (<http://dronedays.fer.hr/en/home/>), the largest event related to the UAV research and industry in Croatia.

2.3.4. Embedding citizens and society

To engage the citizens and society with the scientific research performed at HEIs, an action plan to increase the acceptance of AAS and support participation will be devised. Based on this action plan, current public dissemination events, that HEIs organise and participate in (such as Open-lab days at FSB, Robotic food court at FER, Open Doors Day at FTTS), as well as new ones that will be organised, will be (re)structured to encourage active participation of the public, seeking feedback for ongoing and even recruiting for future research activities of HEIs. Moreover, to spark curiosity and interest of younger generations in aerial systems and to share knowledge in an age-appropriate way, we will plan and organise hands-on UAV workshops at w-HEIs, suitable for primary and secondary school students. Finally, to champion open science, the consortium plans to share knowledge, tools and data throughout and after the project lifetime, not only with academia, but also with industry, end-users, public authorities, citizens, and society as such. To enhance open collaboration between universities and industrial partners in different countries, we will create an Open Remote Laboratory.

3 RESULTS

In this section, several AeroSTREAM events during the first year of the project are shown. We show different types of events that were aimed to cover both research, innovation, and outreach goals. The events included multidisciplinary collaboration between the widening countries and the European technology leaders in the field of aerial robotics.

3.1. AeroSTREAM Summer School

Fly4Future organised a first edition of the AeroSTREAM Summer School in 2022 [10]. The program of the event was full of talks of recognized experts, social events, and trainings. For all the partners the event was live streamed in order to get the talks to all people who were interested. Summer School was held at the Czech Technical University in Prague 1st - 4th August 2022 and had 60 participants (27 online, 33 on site) (Fig. 1). The focus of the AeroSTREAM Summer School 2022 was on systems of cooperating aerial vehicles and swarms, and deployment of MRS in real-world conditions, especially unknown environments.

Eight lecturers from top European universities provided AeroSTREAM students and researchers with the knowledge, ideas, and experience of the best experts in the field of Multi-Robot Systems (MRS) in a comprehensive and effective way. Both the theoretical and practical overview required to bring MRS research from scientific achievements to practical deployment and verification was presented.

Based on the individual interests, researchers were divided into a few groups, to encourage networking possibilities and to gain deeper knowledge in the selected domain of MRS. During the group seminars, tasks relevant to an individual scope of students were discussed and tackled.

Following the lectures, under the supervision of the experienced researchers, the students got an opportunity to implement learned methodology into a fully functional robotic system.

On each day of the Summer School, an evening social program was organised to give the participants the chance to both relax after a tough day of lectures and exercises, and to network among other participants and lecturers which is a great chance for everyone to get valuable contacts. A variety of events took place, including a tour of historic Prague, welcome and farewell parties, and a banquet with a social program.

Figure 1. AeroSTREAM Summer School attendees.

3.2. Drone Days - end-user workshop

DroneDays [11] was a two-day workshop focused on unmanned aerial vehicles held on 4th and 5th May 2023 in Zagreb, Croatia (Fig. 2). The programme consisted of keynote lectures, an exhibition area, and flight demonstrations (Fig. 3) and was focused on unmanned aerial vehicle applications and end-user industries. It is a meeting place for experts from the industry and academia, end-users, as well as regulatory bodies from the region.

This edition of DroneDays was related to three AeroSTREAM application areas: forestry, agriculture and logistics, the lectures were related to these areas and end-users from the areas were invited to participate at the event.

This event also served as a place where AeroSTREAM wHEI researchers could showcase their research topics and results, which was done through lectures by wHEI research, AeroSTREAM and UNIZG-FER LARICS stand at the exhibition area as well as participation in Flight demonstrations, which were open to the public. AeroSTREAM consortium members (CTA and ICENT) also participated in the event visiting the stand and attending different round tables. UNSA and FSB presented their work through lectures.

DroneDays were a very successful event where many new networking connections among researchers and end-users were made. The event again proved to be one of the most important events in Croatia in aerial vehicles.

Figure 2. Audience at the Drone Days end-user workshop

Figure 3. Flight experiments during Drone Days end-user workshop

3.3. Innovation training and short-term visit to Seville

On the 13th and 14th of February 2023, AeroSTREAM researchers from UNIZG-FER, UNIZG-FTTS and ICENT have visited the CTA's facilities, Advanced Centre for Aerospace Technologies (CATEC) facilities, University of Seville (Robotics Laboratory), Seville, Spain.

CTA gave a presentation on its activities in international projects, mainly European projects. A brief presentation was given on the projects which, due to their subject matter, could be of most interest to the attendees, but also on projects in other sectors which are very relevant. Among them, some from the aerospace sector were highlighted. The second day started with a presentation on CTA's activities at cluster level.

In this presentation CTA talked about the companies that are part of the aerospace sector, but also about other sectors related to the AeroSTREAM project and the interests of the participants. Some of the projects funded by CTA to Andalusian companies and research groups were presented, as well as some of the most notorious success stories that have had a major impact at international level.

The next session focused on Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH). Firstly, with an introduction on what a DIH is, what benefits it brings and why they are at the forefront of innovation today. Then, the role of CTA within DIHs was discussed and ideas, experiences and recommendations were shared in general.

In the framework of the Short-Term Visit, participants also attended one of the most important international forums on innovation, technology, and knowledge transfer, the Transfiere forum, where

multiple entities at European level meet annually with a common nexus: innovation. The visit started with a CTA stand and continued with the other ones, exchanging ideas, and discussing opportunities for collaboration with European organisations working on the field of innovation and new technologies.

3.4. Open Remote Laboratory

AeroSTREAM Open Remote Laboratory [12] is a part of AeroSTREAM's Open Science initiative. Open Science's objectives are to enhance open collaboration between universities and industrial partners in different countries, and to share knowledge, tools and data throughout and after the AeroSTREAM project lifetime, not only with academia, but also with industry, end-users, public authorities, citizens, and society as such.

AeroSTREAM Open Remote Laboratory aims to provide an open remote laboratory for autonomous unmanned vehicles. Using existing equipment of AeroSTREAM partners, this Laboratory will allow everyone to remotely conduct experiments on real UAVs free of charge. The experiments will be conducted with AeroSTREAM Open Remote Laboratory platforms with the support of the Laboratory crew. Our crew member will prepare the UAV for flight and personally monitor the safety of the experiment being conducted. The data collected will be open for scientists and the general public.

Open Remote Laboratory provides opportunities for robotic labs from widening countries to experimentally validate UAV-related research with the provided system and technologies. Therefore, the labs can accelerate the research feedback cycle by not needing to develop, test and deploy their own aerial robotic systems.

Furthermore, this project is open to the general public, so it is published and ready to apply on website [11] for any robotic laboratory that wants to support their theoretical research with experimental validation (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Open remote Laboratory website.

Participation in AeroSTREAM Open Remote Laboratory experiments is open to everyone; however, each submission will be assessed based on specific criteria. Experiments that best meet these criteria will be performed live within AeroSTREAM Open Remote Laboratory: Although the experiments are carried out remotely, we encourage everyone to participate in their experiment in person in the Czech Republic.

Going beyond simulation is very exciting. To successfully run your experiment in the real world, you have to prepare it for an environment which can bring unexpected and challenging moments. We've prepared instructions to help you set up your experiment for maximum success.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper showed an innovative and integrating cooperation framework between researchers, technology centres, industries, SMEs, public institutions, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), that was planned within project AeroSTREAM. This paper shows examples of the conducted events in the first

year of the project. The Key Performance Indicators which are followed within the project (such as scientific and innovation activities) show improvement. It is expected that the project will have significant influence on the scientific and innovation capacities of all actors in the R&I system in the widening countries, leading to a modernised and more competitive R&I system, stronger links between academia and business, better career permeability and improved international outreach for all actors. During the activities there was a huge participation of young and senior researchers from w-HEIs, professionals, policy makers, researchers, and enthusiasts to exchange ideas, drive innovation, but also young and senior professionals from Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina and other widening countries from surrounding regions attended the workshops and trainings.

The main novelty of this work is the multidisciplinary collaboration between the widening countries and the European technology leaders in the field of aerial robotics, one of the most promising and widely applied sectors today.

As can be seen from the first results, combining industrial sector activities with academic activities offers a disruptive and enriching vision for all the participating groups, allowing an exponential advance in the knowledge acquired by the participants from the widening countries, and the acquisition of new skills and long-term collaborations by the rest of the countries participating in the AeroSTREAM project.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research program Widening participation and spreading excellence, through project Strengthening Research and Innovation Excellence in Autonomous Aerial Systems (AeroSTREAM) - Grant agreement ID: 101071270.

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